

Visualising the Outcome of Breast Conserving Surgery

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Abstract

Millions of women get diagnosed with breast cancer every year and undergo some form of surgery. This surgery leaves the breast area smaller and deformed and patients are mostly dissatisfied with the aesthetics of the results. Studies have shown that the degree of dissatisfaction can be lowered if women are presented with clear ideas of what they should expect post-surgery.

The results of this project provide a user-friendly mobile application that can display a 3D model of a woman which can be personalized to the patient's specific characteristics, such as the color of the skin. This model can then be used to visualize the likely outcome of the type of surgery that will take place. The breasts of the model can be modified in each quadrant to show the expected changes, based on the position and size of the tumor that will be removed. The patient will therefore be able to better understand how these changes will apply to their own body. Once the expectations are set, the user will be better prepared for the procedure they will have to undergo. Additionally, the application can also provide a useful decision making tool for the patients that are in the position of having to choose what kind of surgery they want performed and whether they wish for reconstructive surgery.

1 Introduction

Breast cancer is currently the most found type of cancer around the world. In the year 2022 alone, 2.3 million women were diagnosed with some form of breast cancer [1]. Out of these millions of patients, some are or will be, treated with surgery. Operations that remove cancerous growth can have many forms, such as total removal (mastectomy) or breast-conserving therapy (BCT). It is a well-recognized fact that post-surgery many women find themselves dissatisfied with the aesthetic appearance of their breasts. However, the degree of dissatisfaction lowers as time passes and the patients accommodate to their new appearance [2]. This fact suggests that if women had some way of better understanding what their breasts will look like after the operation, then they will be less displeased with the outcome. Indeed, trials have shown that patients who were presented with a lot of examples of expected outcomes found the results less surprising and disappointing [3].

The project represents a solution for women who wish to visualize the likely outcome of the surgery they need to undergo. This will take the form of a simple and easy-to-use mobile application that will allow the patient to personalize a 3D model to their appearance and then see the changes that reflect the post-operation aesthetics. A prototype for this project was created beforehand, and throughout the duration of the project, features were added on top of this prototype. The author of the previous work was Ivan Yanakiev, who built it under the supervision of Andrea Capiluppi as a short programming project [4].

The prototype had the following characteristics and features (as can be seen in Figure 1):

- a 3D model of a woman's body
- white skin color on the model
- an open sky background
- the sliders that modify the breast were directly accessible on the screen
- the only UI elements on the screen were the three sliders

Figure 1: Application prototype

In order to improve upon this prototype, answers were found to research questions regarding the way in which the breast is deformed. Additionally, multiple skin colors were found for the mesh, with the intent of making the 3D model more adjustable. Lastly, a simple and user-friendly interface for the application was researched and implemented. Details of exactly what features were added, as well as explanations of the implementation and the reasoning behind them can be found in Chapter 5.

This project is of great importance as it will bring comfort to a vast number of women around the globe and provide a solution to a well-recognised problem. At the moment, doctors who wish to help patients see the likely outcome of the surgery have to resort to using 2D pictures of women who have already gone through the operation or simply using words to describe the changes that will occur. This is not ideal as it does not incorporate the personal characteristics of the patient and leaves them with only very vague ideas.

Once the application is made available to users, millions of women around the world will stand to benefit from the 3D visualization software. Doctors will be able to edit the model according to the surgery that will be performed and patients will be able to see a personalized figure specific to them. It is expected that this experience will help women better understand what changes they should prepare for and help with the transition from before to post-surgery. The application will serve its greatest impact during the decision-making process of the patient. Numerous patients are presented with the option of choosing whether they want a mastectomy or BCT. Along with this choice, they have to decide if they want to undergo reconstruction surgeries as well. During these times, the application can provide valuable information to the user. The flowchart in Figure 2 shows the places within this process where the application will provide the most help, highlighted in blue. Additionally, three nodes have also been highlighted in orange. These represent the decision that a patient might want to ponder in the privacy of their own home, without a doctor. For this use case, a second version of the application is considered. This other version would allow patients to see the expected outcome without requiring the help of a doctor or surgeon. A more detailed flowchart that also includes the reconstructive options can be found in Appendix Section B.

1.1 Research Questions

To summarize, this thesis focuses on the following problems:

- Q1. To what extent is it possible to edit the mesh to accurately modify the size and shape of the breasts in accordance with the surgery it is trying to represent?
- Q2. In what ways should the model be adjustable in order to best represent patients?
- Q3. What is a deformation model that can better represent the surgeries that will be depicted and add to the realism of the application?

1.2 Thesis Outline

Throughout this paper, multiple aspects of the project will be detailed and explained.

Chapter 2 delves into the research that was performed and elaborates on the current state of the art with regard to the topic at hand.

Chapter 3 showcases multiple interviews and conversations that were carried out with the purpose of better understanding the experience of a patient and the insight of a surgeon.

Chapter 4 will provide a clear explanation of the necessary information about Unreal Engine 5, which was used to build the application.

Chapter 5 will go into more detail about state of the application before the start of the project, as well as the implementation and the choices that were made during that process.

Chapter 6 elaborates on the ideas that were thought of during this project but were pushed on and therefore became future work, including details about a deformation equation that was found. It also documents some important notes made by the doctor and patients that were interviewed.

Chapter 7 is a conclusion to this paper and the project as a whole and will touch upon the most important aspects.

Figure 2: Simplified flowchart of the choices patients have after diagnosis. The blue nodes represent the moments in which the application can be of use. The orange nodes represent the moments when an application could be used without the assistance of a doctor.

2 Research

2.1 Findings

One factor that influences women's satisfaction with the outcome of their surgery (be it complete mastectomy or breast-conserving treatment) is their understanding of the procedure and the likely aesthetics post-procedure. A review of multiple studies has found that patients who were provided with decision aids were less likely to be unsatisfied with their results [3]. The analysed studies were all medical trials that used multiple different "decision aids", such as booklets, pictures, educational videos about breast cancer, and videos of women who had already gone through the surgery. The patients who participated in the trials had been diagnosed with early-stage cancer or stages I or II of breast cancer. All studies concluded some amount of improvement in the patients' understanding of the procedure and their dissatisfaction post-surgery. However, while the decision aids helped the patients, they were not personalized aids and did not allow the patients to see what their own breasts might look like after the surgery.

Patients can benefit from being able to see personalized outcomes of the surgery, catered to their respective bodies. One study has found a significant difference between the use of personalized 3D models and simple 2D pictures of other women [5]. Women were found to feel more confident in their understanding of the possible outcome of the surgery when they were shown 3D simulations of their own breasts compared to being shown pictures of the outcomes of other women. For the purposes of that study, the 3D models were created using Vectra XT and Mirror. The Vectra XT system and the Mirror software had to be adapted and stretched beyond their intended use cases due to the fact that there is no software available to do this exact task at the moment.

The Mirror software as well as the Vectra XT camera system are designed for simulating the outcome of breast implant surgery. The latter has been found to be accurate when compared to the actual outcome of the procedure [6]. These are just examples of existing solutions regarding breast-enhancing operations. By contrast, there is no software at the moment that can provide the same functionality for patients who are about to undergo breast-conserving therapy (BCT) or mastectomy.

This gap in the industry has been noticed and attempts have been made to identify a satisfactory solution. To this extent, the process of taking the pictures needed for the simulations may be eased by using simple and accessible hardware [7]. In order to be able to model the post-surgery deformations, the outcome has to be predicted in some way [8] and attempts have been made towards obtaining a regression model using machine learning [9]. However, even with these achievements, there is no single software, application, or product to provide the needed functionality.

It is important to mention some works that stand out. Firstly, doctor Vavourakis et al have managed to create software that uses MRI scans and physics equations to describe the outcome of the wound healing process after the patients undergo surgery [10]. This uses 3D meshes that are generated using the MRI scans of the patient, which are then passed to the computational model. The resulting mesh can then be displayed using already existing open-source software. Secondly, H. Zolfagharnasab et al who used the work of doctor Vavourakis to validate their own results [9]. They used machine learning to try to predict the outcome of the surgeries and their results were impactful. This also allowed them to provide a rough estimation of what aspects most impact the deformation of the breasts. According to their findings, breast density, and tumor position are of the highest importance. However, it is very

important to note that while these results show progress in terms of predicting or calculating the outcome of the surgeries, they still do not offer a solution to patients. The software they have produced can at best be used by tech-savvy doctors who have enough experience to use all the necessary parts of the system. A patient should not be asked to use such software to understand what they will look like at the end of a procedure.

In an attempt to better understand the work of Doctor Vavourakis, a short conversation was had with him. The notes of this can be found in the Appendix Section A. Within this talk, some very important questions were asked. It was found that the software which his team developed is quite computationally intensive, as could be expected considering the functionalities it provides. This means that running such a software on a mobile device would be quite a complicated task on its own, and his team has never tried it. Additionally, they have never conducted a parameter study in order to find out which variables most affect the changes in the breast, but he was still able to provide a list of observed priorities. This was:

1. Breast density
2. Tumor size
3. Tumor location

This conversation further confirmed that the software was not meant to be patient-facing. Instead, it was meant to help surgeons better understand and visualize the location of a tumor and the healing process post-surgery. However, this software provides a good base for future applications, which can use it as verification that the displayed results are accurate.

2.2 Search process

The literature used in this section was found by using the following keywords in the University of Groningen SmartCat engine: "3D modeling" AND "torso" AND "breast cancer". Additionally, the following phrase was applied to the Google and DuckDuckGo search engines: "software for modeling breast cancer removal surgery". Some more impactful papers were found by searching the citations within the papers that were originally found. Similarly, others were found by searching for papers that cited impactful papers. These searches resulted in some computer science related papers that were attempting to find and implement solutions to this need, like models for predicting breast deformation and ways for creating 3D models of patients for cheaper. Other found papers were studies or summaries of medical trials where different methods of informing women were tested against a control group (which generally represented the current procedure used by doctors when presenting pre-surgery information). Other material, such as the existing project that will be expanded upon was provided by the supervisor of this project, Andrea Capiluppi.

3 Stakeholder study

In order to best understand the needs of the patients and doctors that will be using the application, interviews, and conversations were carried out in the beginning preparatory phase of the project. In this chapter, these conversations and the conclusions that were drawn from them will be described and elaborated upon. Appendix Section A contains the notes that were taken during the talks with each person.

3.1 Dr. Mahyar Foumani

Doctor Foumani is a surgeon who deals with reconstructive surgery and has first-hand experience with patients who are suffering from the aesthetic outcome of breast cancer surgeries. He had valuable input about what the application should be able to provide. At the end of the conversation with him, it was clear that the following features were of great importance:

- The application should be as realistic as possible
- The model of the woman should be very customizable, as to make the patient feel represented

Doctor Foumani also confirmed that there are indeed currently no applications that provide these very needed functionalities. He also explained that such software is also necessary for the reconstructive surgeries that the patients go through. This shows that even though there is some progress in this regard for cosmetic surgeries (such as Vectra XT and Crisalix), there is nothing that provides help for patients with medical needs.

3.2 Former patients

Three women who previously suffered from breast cancer and had to undergo surgery to remove parts of the breast were interviewed with the intent of understanding what the experience was like for them. Additionally, they were introduced to the prototype of the application, as well as told of the features that will be added, and they were asked whether or not they would have liked to use the app at the time.

The overwhelming conclusion that had to be drawn after the three conversations was that patients are in a prolonged state of shock ever since the diagnosis is set. All three women mentioned that their primary concern is surviving and returning to health in order to care for their children and family. However, considering that the survival rates of breast cancer are above 90%, it is believed that better-informed patients will be able to better comprehend the situation they are in and understand that their lives are not threatened in most cases. To this extent, the application being built as part of this project would be well suited to belong in an informational package that is handed out to patients.

Additionally, they expressed a common opinion that society is not very well suited to offering moral support for people who find themselves in situations like theirs. While friends and family try to help as best they can, strangers prefer to not talk about this topic. This is also reflected in standards that are placed on the woman of the family in certain cases. All this can make patients scared of the outcome of the surgeries, so setting expectations from the start is very important.

With regard to surgery preparations, none of the women were shown anything that described what their breasts will look like. One woman was shown a hand-drawn image of what part of the breast

would be cut, and a different woman took it upon herself to search on the internet for pictures of former patients. When shown the prototype and asked their opinion, the reactions were positive. Even while all three women felt like the aesthetics were not of the highest importance to them personally, they acknowledged that the application offered important information to users and would have liked to have been able to use it.

At the end of the interviews, a list of possible improvements and considerations was composed. Some of these have been implemented as part of the project and the rest will be noted for future improvements:

- Ability to customize body type or size [Section 6.2]
- More inclusive breast sizes
- A disclaimer about the shock factor of the results that are modeled [Section 6.3]
- A closer view of the breasts [Section 5.3]
- A more intuitive user interface [Section 5.3]

4 Background

This chapter provides some basic information about the software that was used to build the application. It details a short introduction and a small example of the most used parts of the engine.

4.1 Unreal Engine 5

The mobile application being built provided some requirements with regard to the software that would be used to build it. The engine had to be able to export to all mobile operating systems and had to be intuitive and easy to use. Additionally, it had to be able to clearly render the changes in the breast area of a model. For these reasons, the prime candidate became Unreal Engine 5. It is a cutting-edge development engine and it gained immense popularity due to its impressive capabilities and versatility. This means that it will definitely be able to handle all the functionalities that the application requires, the most important of which is the ability to run and render the deformation model.

One of the most important features of Unreal Engine 5 is the ability to provide background logic to the application through Blueprints. This is a powerful visual scripting system that allows applications to be fully developed without the need of writing C++ code in the traditional way. Within this system, nodes that represent objects, functions, and variables are connected to each other to create the rules and logic of the application. As can be seen in the example below, Figure 3, it is also possible to add comments around nodes in order to explain what that section of the logic does. Additionally, it is also possible to create new custom elements, including events, functions, and variables.

Considering all of this, Blueprints offer an amazing way of setting the logic of the application, allowing for both beginners and experienced developers to quickly pick up the system and contribute to the software. On top of this, if later on it is decided that Blueprints lack a needed functionality, it is always possible to introduce classic C++ code into the application. All this flexibility clearly shows that Unreal Engine 5 is an excellent fit for this project.

Figure 3: Blueprints example showing custom events, variables, setters, and a comment. Taken from part of the logic that deals with the changing of skin color from the application.

5 Implementation

Before the implementation of the upgrades to the application is explained in detail, it is important to first understand the starting point of this project, the prototype. To this end, the basic features that needed improvement are described below.

The implementation provided a scalar way for the breast size to be modified, which was a good proof of concept, but definitely required improvement and further development. Initially, this was accomplished with the use of an extra bone within the skeletal mesh of the model. This is not extremely unusual, as within the field of game design, bones are often used to represent moving parts of a model, even though they do not match the human anatomy. Following this principle, we propose adding more bone to the breast area, so that the deformation can be more finely tuned. This will greatly increase the possibilities in which a breast can be altered, allowing for a better representation of the surgery. The implementation of these details can be found in Section 5.1.

It was decided that the model requires more personalization and that the first step in that regard would be the option of selecting a skin color. To this extent, six skin colors were added to a separate menu as options for the users. The process of implementing this and a description of the decisions made with regard to this can be found in Section 5.2.

Additionally, the background and user interface that were used needed to be changed. The model needs to be placed in a space that would not surprise the user, so a simple room, furnished to look like a basic doctor's office was created. The user interface needs to be intuitive and also provide a clear view of the model. The old interface covers about half the screen and makes it so that the user needs to move around the space in order to correctly frame the breast of the model. For this reason, a menu with options was created, which allows all the UI elements to stay consistent. This also means that it is possible to exit the breast editing menu and be able to fully see the model, without having the buttons and sliders cover the screen. More details about these features and their implementation can be found in Section 5.3.

5.1 Breast deformation

The prototype that was provided only allowed for a linear motion of each breast. As a result, when the sliders were used, the changes affected onto the model looked more like changing the size of a healthy breast and less like the effects of cancer surgery. After the conversations with Doctor Mahyar Foumani and Doctor Vasileios Vavourakis, it was clear that one of the most important factors that determine the look of the outcome is the position of the tumor within the breast. In order to better describe this within the application, it was decided to implement the ability to scale each quadrant of the breast. This is because the location of a tumor is usually described by the quadrant it belongs to. The quadrants have the following names:

- Upper left quadrant - ULQ
- Upper right quadrant - URQ
- Lower left quadrant - LLQ
- Lower right quadrant - LRQ

The first step in this process was to edit the skeleton of the 3D model in order to fit the new requirements. This was achieved by using Blender, a software dedicated to 3D modeling and rendering. Since the goal was to be able to separately scale each quadrant of the breast, a total of six new bones had to be added. This means that now each breast has four bones that can be scaled, eight in total. The new skeleton can be seen in Figure 4. Once the bones were in place and ready, the new model had to be imported into Unreal Engine 5, and the old 3D model could be removed.

Figure 4: New skeleton with four bones per breast (one per quadrant)

In order to implement this functionality, some changes needed to be made to the function that handled the scaling of the breast. The situation presented an opportunity for refactoring some of the logic of the application. This function was originally created to be used to change either one of the two breasts. If it was simply scaled so that it works for 4 quadrants, the result would be quite messy. This can be seen

in Figure 5. In order to avoid this, a sort of refactoring was performed on the nodes of the function, so that the resulting Blueprint was much more readable and understandable. This was achieved by breaking down the logic into two functions. The new Blueprints which have much fewer nodes and connections can be seen in Figure 6 and Figure 7. The parts of the old logic that are highlighted in orange were extracted and placed into the first function. This way the nodes are no longer repeated for no reason. The rest of the nodes from the original version deal with identifying what quadrant should be scaled. This was done with lots of if-statements. This logic is now accomplished in the second function and switch-statements were used to replace the multiple if-statements that cluttered the space. Of course, adding more parts of the breast that can be scaled meant adding more sliders to the user interface. This was not a particularly difficult task, but the increase in sliders meant that an even larger portion of the screen was taken up by them. To remediate this, the sliders were placed inside a menu that can be toggled on and off. For more details about this, see Section 5.3.

Figure 5: Example of a badly organized Blueprint

to implement the functionality of choosing the skin color of the model. The prototype that was provided at the beginning of the project did not use any particular material and as such, a default white material was chosen by the modeling engine. In order to remediate this, multiple skin-like materials had to be created from scratch and assigned to the model. When it became time to choose which and how many skin tones will be implemented, a well-used skin color categorisation method was used. The Fitzpatrick scale provides a good starting point for this project and uses six groups to which a skin color can belong to [11]. The tones of this scale ensure that the application will provide enough options for both Dutch and international users [12]. This was an important goal, as it widens the possible audience of the software and means that the application can even be launched outside the Netherlands.

Within Unreal Engine 5, materials are a type of asset that is used to describe the appearance of an object that is placed in the world. Materials contain information such as the color, texture, and other properties of the object it is trying to represent. As with most parts of Unreal Engine 5, materials are created and edited with Blueprints. This is done in the form of nodes of vectors, variables, and constants that are assigned to the final material node. This process can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 8: The custom event that can be triggered to change to skin color number 4

Figure 9: Blueprint nodes of a skin tone button

Figure 10: Example of a material Blueprint

For the purposes of the skin tones of the 3D model used by the application, it was necessary to create new materials for each skin color that was added. Each new material uses a color node to describe one of the color groups of the Fitzpatrick scale. Additionally, a roughness constant is added to make the material look appropriate. Without the added roughness, the skin would be shiny and plastic-like. The resulting Blueprint can be seen in Figure 10. Once all six materials were ready, one of them was assigned to the model as the default color. In order to make the rest of the colors available to the user, new elements had to be added to the user interface. For details of how user interfaces are created, see Section 5.3. A menu containing buttons for each available skin color was introduced to make changing the appearance of the model possible. Each button has the same color as the skin it represents so that the user has an idea of the colors they can choose from. In order to maintain

consistency between the material and the button colors, the skin tones were saved using an internal ability available in Unreal Engine 5. Within the Color Picker menu of the Engine, which is available from multiple parts of the software, it is possible to create and save new color themes. Using this, the chosen colors of the Fitzpatrick scale were saved to be used throughout the application. This can be seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11: The skin tones saved within the Color Picker menu

Once the user interface was done and the materials were ready, it was necessary to connect the two, so that when a button was pressed, the actual skin color of the model was changed. To this end, new custom events had to be added to the Blueprint of the 3D model of the woman. Using these, whenever the event was triggered, the material assigned to the visible model would be changed to the called one. This means a custom event was necessary for each skin tone, resulting in six new custom events. One such node can be seen in Figure 8. All that remained was to ensure that when a button was pressed, the custom even related to it was triggered. This can be seen in Figure 9.

5.3 User interface and user experience

When the existing prototype was presented it was clear that the user interface needed an upgrade. The current state of the UI meant that about half of the screen was covered by the sliders used to change the sizes of the breast. This was not ideal since it is desired that the 3D model be clearly visible to the user. This meant that menus needed to be introduced to the structure of the user interface. This allows the sliders to be opened, set and then closed so that the model of the woman remains the center of attention when necessary. Additionally, the open sky background was quite jarring and disconnected from the goal of the application. In order to remediate this, the background was replaced with that of a doctor's office. The goal of this was to put the model in the same environment as the target user of the application. On top of this, in order to provide the patients and doctors with clear information about what is being displayed, an informational text has been added to the screen.

Within Unreal Engine 5, in order to create or edit elements of the user interface, one must make use of UI Widgets. These provide a way for the developer to easily drag and drop basic elements onto the screen of the application, such as buttons, sliders, and text blocks. On top of this, once the elements are added to the screen, the developer can switch to the graph view, where it is possible to edit the Blueprint of the widget. Here, it is possible to connect nodes to events that belong to any of the elements on the screen. For example, in the case of a button, the most important event is that of it being pressed. A Blueprint of such a case can be seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Blueprint nodes of a Back button

For the purposes of this application, multiple widgets had to be created, and connections between them had to be implemented. The main screen of the application now presents buttons for the multiple menus that are available to the user. This is also the screen that will be used to see the breasts in detail as this is where the screen is least covered. From this menu, it is possible to navigate to others, where the user can change and customize the 3D model. This is achieved by using the Is Pressed event of a corresponding button. Once a button is pressed, the new widget is added to the screen, and the old one is removed. This is done in the Blueprints of the widgets and can be seen in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Blueprint nodes of a menu button

During the interviews with the patients, they mentioned the fact the visible sky in the background was quite weird, and that it made the application feel detached. This made it clear that the model needed to be placed in an indoor environment. Considering that having the model be placed in an empty box would also be weird and jarring, it was decided to place the model in a simple replica of a doctor’s office. In order to create the doctor’s office background, basic props that are available in the Engine were used. The already existing walls were made taller, a ceiling was put in place and windows were added. As part of the interior design, lamps were introduced, and a desk set up with chairs was arranged in the corner. A plant and a pedestal for the 3D model were added as finishing touches. The final result can be seen in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Background of the 3D model

The informational text is connected to the sliders of the breast area and simply shows the current percentage of each. This text belongs to a widget that is never removed from the screen as the information should be visible from all menus. Creating this widget required a small change in the background of the logic, as the percentage of the slider now needed to be available to other parts of the system. To accommodate this, the current percentage of each slider is now stored as a variable in the Blueprint of the 3D model itself. This is done by updating the stored information every time a slider is moved, and it allows all parts of the system to access this information. The results of this can be seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Screenshot showing the information widget in use

6 Future work

It is always important to consider ways in which the current application can be improved upon as future projects. For this reason, this chapter will elaborate upon the ideas that were found during this project but were not implemented due to time constraints. In some of these cases, the implementation has already been thought of and will be detailed below. In other cases, they represent requirements that were extracted from the conversations with the surgeon and the patients.

6.1 Deformation equation

Even though the changes in the breast can be guessed and estimated using the size and position of the tumor, as well as the density of the breast, hard work has been done to try to find an equation that describes the precise deformation of the breast area after surgery. In this endeavor, the work of Doctor Vasileios Vavourakis et al, among others, deserves elaboration [10]. The team of Doctor Vavourakis has managed to put together an equation that simulates the looks of the breasts after the wound healing process. On top of this, once the equation was established and the constants had been decided, they were able to implement a software that uses MRI-based meshes of the patients' breasts to visually display the predicted outcome. The meshes do require the use of third-party open-source software to be visualised. This chapter provides a simplified explanation of the equation with the purpose of highlighting the elements that are used in it. For a deeper understanding, it is recommended to see the cited paper and the references therein.

6.1.1 Equation

The starting form of the equation can be seen in Equation 1, but it is important to note that from here, most of the terms can be expanded upon. This means that the equations tend to cascade out to a point where a lot of constants and variables are involved.

$$\nabla \cdot [\mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{S}] + \rho_{0, \text{tissue}} \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0} \quad (1)$$

Here the basic meaning and a short description of most of the terms will be provided.

- ∇ - called divergence, it is a measure of a force's tendency to converge toward or diverge from a point
- \mathbf{F} - deformation matrix, represents the actual transformations that need to be applied
- \mathbf{S} - 2nd Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor, the determinant of the energy function w.r.t. to the stress tensor
- $\rho_{0, \text{tissue}}$ - the density of the breast, described as the ratio between fibroglandular and adipose tissue
- \mathbf{b} - the force vector per unit mass, in the case of a standing 3D model, this can be thought of as the gravity pulling the breasts down

6.1.2 Explanation

Looking at the equation and the legend found some basic inferences can be made. In this section, these will be explained in simple terms.

The elements **F** and **S** in combination basically represent the forces that drag parts of the breast in certain directions after the surgery. Once the tumor is removed, the space left behind must be filled by the tissue around it. Therefore, a big part of Equation 1 is just the movement of said tissue and the way the breast will look after the wound is completely healed. In the current implementation of the application, this is represented by the movement of a bone from the corresponding quadrant of the breast. The shifting of the adjacent tissue is visible even now because the mesh of the model stretches and creates a smooth transition from the intact parts to the smaller parts of the breast.

As part of Equation 1 the elements $\rho_{0, \text{tissue}}$ and **b** are combined to include the effects of gravity on different parts of the breast. It will represent the way in which denser parts of the breast are more sturdy and less affected by gravity, as opposed to the more adipose parts of the breast, which are more prone to sagging. In the current implementation of the application, this is assured by the position of the bones within the breast. The bones are placed at an angle, pointing down, so that when the size of the bone is changed, the mesh will move in such a way that looks affected by gravity. As a future improvement, a slider for inputting the known density of the breast could be added. Once a density is given, that information could slightly change the effect of the movement of the bones so that it more accurately represents the expected outcome.

The deformation equation described would be of great benefit if it is implemented inside the application. There are lots of options for how this could be achieved, but in this section, only two will be elaborated:

- Editing the vertices of the mesh
- Scaling the bones of the breast

Depending on how exactly the logic of the application is implemented, either one of the options above could be selected. Changing the position of the vertices of the mesh while the application is running is possible in Unreal Engine 5, through the use of a plugin that can be easily installed. Once this is done, the results of the equation would have to be transformed onto coordinates for the vertices. However, if the other option is chosen, it would only mean upgrading the current state of the application. Some bones, eight to be precise are already in place. If the results of the equation are more precise than that, it would require the addition of more bones to the skeleton of the model. And again, once the results of the equation are obtained, they would have to be transformed into scalars that can be applied to the bones, in order to visualize the changes to the breast area.

6.2 Body types

The prototype given at the beginning of the project provided a way for the user to adjust the hips of the model using a slider. This was a very basic attempt at allowing the user to provide a body type to the 3D model. In order to improve this, it is suggested to implement the ability to select one of the three scientifically recognised body types [13]:

- Ectomorph

- Endomorph
- Mesomorph

These represent the three groups into which the genetic structure of the body can be classified. If these were to be implemented as three simple buttons that can be added to a menu in the user interface, the patients will be able to select the body type that best represents them and therefore better understand how the change will affect their own body. In order to better understand the three body types, they have been rendered in Blender on the same model that was used in the application. The results can be seen in Figure 16.

Regarding the implementation of this feature, it can be achieved quite easily. The bones of the hips and shoulder / collarbone need to only be scaled. Since the breasts are adjusted by scaling bones, there already exists a code that performs such a task. The nodes from the Blueprints would only need to be copied in the right place and slightly adjusted to change the correct bones. After this is done, all that remains is to add buttons to a new widget and add the logic that connects the pressing of the button to the changes in the skeleton.

Figure 16: The three body types rendered in Blender. From left to right: ectomorph, endomorph, and mesomorph

6.3 Scalable realism

During the conversations with Doctor Foumani and one of the patients, a certain feature was mentioned that should be documented. That is the ability to scale the detail and realism presented by the application. The reasoning behind this idea is that some patients seem quite scared and would rather not be presented with all the details of their surgery, while others are more straightforward and would like to have all the information that is available. In order to accommodate this, a number of options

could be considered.

Firstly, the patient might be presented with two options, a button for a more cartoon-ish presentation and a button for a more realistic appearance to the application. The changes between the two can span multiple aspects. Of course, the detail with which the deformation of the breast is calculated is the first to be considered. One such difference could be that the less realistic version uses the quadrants that are available at the moment, while the more realistic uses an equation that changes the vertices of the mesh itself, as described in Section 6.1. On top of this, the material used by the 3D model could change too, in order to reflect which part of the application is being used. A simple uni-color material could be used for the cartoon-ish version, while the more detailed implementation could use a more human-like material that includes texture to the skin and better presented all the parts of the body.

Secondly, instead of only two application versions that can be selected through buttons, a slider could be used. This would therefore present the user with what feels like an infinite number of options for the detail of the presentation. From here, the patient could choose what they find to be the perfect amount of detail and use that. This option would be harder to implement as it would have to somehow perfectly transition between the two styles mentioned before.

7 Conclusion

It is important to remember that this application is the first of its kind and that once it is available to the public, it will help millions of women make the tough decisions that they are forced to make. Through the research that was performed, it was learned that there exists software that has similar functionality but can not be used for this exact purpose. These are applications that allow the visualisation of the outcome of breast implant surgery. However, due to the fact that tumor position and size vary for every patient, the already existing software has not been expanded in this direction.

In order to achieve its goal, this project was composed of a number of tasks that had to be completed. By the end of the project timeline, the following targets have been reached:

- Carrying out interviews with a doctor and patients to better understand and document the actual requirements of the future users of the application
- Improving the user interface by creating menus, completely re-doing the background, and moving the position of the camera
- Improving the customization of the 3D model by implementing the possibility of changing the skin color of the mesh
- Improving the detail of the breast scaling by increasing the number of bones and sliders by a factor of four
- Finding and describing an equation that is able to predict the deformation of the breast, which can later be implemented into the application

The application was implemented in Unreal Engine 5, following the previous work given at the beginning. All the logic that was added was expressed through nodes in Blueprints. The 3D model was initially created and later edited to add more bones to the breast area using Blender. This means that the model is not engine specific and that it can be imported into other software if so desired.

As a last step of the project, doctor Mahyar Foumani was contacted again and asked to provide feedback on the current state of the application. After having seen the new features that were added, he noted the following aspects. The result of the project provides a very good starting point for the application. It can be used to quickly and clearly understand the expected outcome of a breast-conserving surgery. The application, as it is right now, could be used to show patients a demonstration of the final goal of the bigger project. This could be useful in terms of being able to set up a patient trial in the future for example. The doctor was also able to provide some ideas of how he sees the final result of the project. It includes features such as the ability to scan the skin of the patient in order to obtain their personal skin color, the ability of the mesh to show the results of radiotherapy, and the use of augmented reality. The AR would be used to show the expected changes directly on the body of the patient. Overall, the doctor was happy with the progress of the application and the way in which the deformation of the breast is realised at the moment.

The duration of the project was 420 hours, around ten weeks, during which the above goals were achieved. During this time, the research and the writing of this thesis were also performed. All of the work was done under the supervision and help of Prof. Dr. Andrea Capiluppi and Dr. Mahyar Foumani.

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Appendices

A Interview notes

A.1 Dr. Mahyar Foumani

- he is a breast surgeon
- he likes our application and would like to see something similar for reconstructive surgery
- he thinks an augmented reality feature to the app would be good
- he thinks the app should be as realistic as possible, and very personalisable

A.2 Ana-Maria Ionescu

- had a sectorectomy surgery
- she received no description of what the outcome will look like
- she did not suffer a big psychological impact
- her surgeon did not know how much he would have to remove prior to the surgery taking place. This was due to the fact that they did not do an extra scan that would have provided that information
- she then had a follow-up surgery at a private clinic. There she was shown a hand drawing made by the doctor as she was trying to explain what they will be doing to her during the surgery
- the second surgery made her scar grow in size
- due to the kind of tissue that was removed, there is a 40% chance that her arm will not drain properly and grow in diameter
- throughout the whole process Maria was most concerned about living and did not care much about the aesthetics of the outcome. She said "Living is what matters!"
- the application we are making could have helped her understand what to expect

A.3 Anca Titu

- had a sectorectomy surgery
- had tubular cancer, which is slightly less aggressive
- her arm that corresponds to the breast that was operated on can not be fully used any more
- she feels like she has less energy since the surgery, even tho it has been many years since
- she did not receive much moral support
- the surgeon did not know the full situation before the surgery had begone
- friends and family were a really big help

- now, after the surgery, she is not interested in a cosmetic surgery for her breast
- her scar is not pretty, but it is "acceptable"
- she does not care that her breast looks a bit different
- she feels like society does not help you. They ridicule you and make fun of your situation
- "I had to raise my children" - this was her main concern
- in Romania there are not enough testing centers and it is very crowded
- she was shown a drawing of her breast and where the cancer was. The drawing was made by hand by the surgeon and was very vague
- the aesthetics of the outcome were never addressed by the doctors
- she thinks our application can help patients decide if they want the surgery (she has heard of families breaking apart due to the bad aesthetics of the outcome)
- she thinks that our application can help some people, but it also might scare others

A.4 Laura Gherman

- she had a rapidly advancing type of cancer
- she cares way more about remaining healthy and not very much about the aesthetics of the outcome. She felt like that was not very important
- she does not look at the scar and breast very often
- she had only very short conversations with her doctor, where only the bare minimum was explained
- she found pictures of other patients online
- she thinks the application should show the scar
- she now had problems with her spine as the weight of the remaining breast is pulling on her unevenly

A.5 Dr. Vasileios Vavourakis

- the things that most affect the changes of the breast are (in order):
 1. breast density
 2. tumor size
 3. tumor location
- he is curious about whether FEB3 can run on mobile device
- they did not carry out a parameter study because their program doesn't use the parameters directly and in order to do that they would need to take a survey of the population and the users of the program
- he would be interested in a partnership with prof. Andrea Capiluppi

B Surgery flowchart

Figure 17: Initial options flowchart

Figure 18: Secondary options flowchart